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“A PET”

He's small, won't ever grow tall,
He barks, his echo fills the hall.
Why did we have him? Just a pet—
A passing thought, a brief regret.

One morning he brings me a toy,
I didn't expect it would come with joy.
I hear him whimper as the night has set,
What can we do? He's just a pet.

With gentle snuffles, he draws me near,
He runs to greet me, full of cheer.
Now I come home and search the door,
For the little soul I can't ignore.

Now when I'm away, my heart feels tight,
These loud worries in my head, I can't fight.
Now I wish I wouldn't forget,
How could I say “he's just a pet.”